

Effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding importance of mental health among B. Sc nursing students at Government College of Nursing Dewan-bagh Srinagar, Kashmir

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Abstract

The study aims to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding importance of mental health among B.Sc Nursing Students of first year at Govt. College of Nursing Dewan-bagh, GMC Srinagar, Kashmir. The methodology of the presents study was a pre experimental one pretest post test research design. Sample size of the study was 30 selected with purposive sampling technique. Self-structured knowledge questionnaire on importance of mental health was used for data collection. Data collection was done in the month of October 2022.

Results: The study findings reveal with regard to the group the pre - test value is 11.6000 (SD±3.42) and the post-test value is 20.8667 (SD ±2.50). The difference between knowledge scores of pre-test and post-test was found statistically significant at P value 0.001. Hence structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding importance of mental health among B.Sc Nursing students of first year was effective and has increased the level of knowledge among them. There was a statistically significant association between pre-test levels of knowledge of samples with socio demographic variables (age, gender, domicile and source of information).

Conclusion: The study concluded that the structured teaching programme was effective in enhancing the knowledge regarding importance of mental health among B.Sc Nursing students of first year students studying at Govt. College of Nursing Dewan-bagh, GMC Srinagar, Kashmir.

Keywords: Structured Teaching Program; Knowledge; Importance; Mental health.

1. Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO): Mental health is a state of mental well-being that enable people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community. "The WHO states that mental health is "more than just the absence of mental disorders or disabilities." Peak mental health is not only about managing active conditions but also looking after ongoing wellness and happiness. Social and financial

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circumstances, adverse childhood experiences, biological factors, and underlying medical conditions can all shape a person’s mental health.

It is important to know that good mental health depends on a delicate balance of factors and that several elements may contribute to developing these disorders ¹The mental health of university students is evidenced a growing problem globally². After graduating from higher secondary school students come across with a number of issues (e.g., dormitory life, study stress, lack of time management, unhealthy eating habits, sleeping disorders, smoking, problematic internet usage, and sedentary behavior etc.) in their new academic setting³. In this period of transition, students are struggling to deal with an intellectual and social hurdles of university/collage studies, which is essential for their preparation to complete their professional degrees with the development of professional knowledge, skill and experience.^{4, 5}. ⁶Furthermore, the university/collage environment possess lot of surprises that may be unbearable and bring unexpected problems for some fresher students, and they may lack the psychological resilience to deal with such situations^{4,7}. Therefore after a given period students may experience severe stress, anxiety, self-harm, including suicidal ideation or attempt, and so on.

1.1. Need for the study

The World Mental Health Survey conducted across 21 countries among college students reported that 20.3% had mental health issues in the preceding 12 months ⁸. Similar findings has been reported from various States of India^{9,10,11}. It is found that 75 per cent severe mental illnesses are significantly experienced by the age of 25 year ¹². Thus, collage students are likely to experience an onset of severe mental health issues within their collage /university time ¹³. One study found that 45% of Kashmir's adult population (1.8 million) was suffering from some form of mental distress. There is a high prevalence of depression (41%), anxiety (26%), post-traumatic stress disorder (19%), and 47% had experienced some sort of trauma.¹⁴Another study found that the prevalence of childhood disorders were 22–27% (aged 8–14 years¹⁵. A retrospective study on suicide recorded an increase of more than 250% in the number of suicide attempts between 1994 and 2012.¹⁶ This emphasizes the need for primary and secondary preventive strategies, as well as the creation of necessary and suitable support services for this particular group. Therefore, Researchers found that fresher students admitting for Bsc nursing course must be given knowledge regarding mental health and simultaneously raise awareness among university students to help them in their mental health issues ¹⁷ through anti-stigma campaigns and public education via schools, colleges and the media. Thus there was a need to assess “Effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding importance of mental health among B.sc nursing students at Govt. College of Nursing Dewan-bagh Srinagar, Kashmir”

Objectives

- To assess the pre-test knowledge score regarding importance mental health among B.sc nursing First year students..
- To evaluate the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Program on knowledge regarding importance of mental health among B.sc nursing First year students.
- To find out an association between pre-test knowledge scores with selected demographic variables (Gender, Residence, source of information)

1.2. Hypothesis

- There will be significant knowledge regarding importance of Mental Health among Bsc Nursing students.
- There will be no significant association of pretest score and demographic variables.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

Pre-experimental Research design was used for the study as Pre-test and Post-Test Design

O1	X	O2
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Where:

O1 – Pre – test

X – Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding importance of Mental Health.

O2 – Post – test

2.2. Setting

The study was conducted at Govt. College of Nursing Dewan-bagh, GMC Srinagar, Kashmir.

2.3. Sample

Sample for the present study were B. sc nursing students.

2.3.1. Inclusion Criteria

- B.Sc nursing First year fresher students.
- Who will be present during data collection period?
- Who are interested in participation?

2.3.2. Exclusion Criteria

- Who are not present during data collection period?
- Who are not interested to participate in the study?
- B.Sc nursing 2nd year, 3rd year & 4th year.

2.3.3. Sampling technique

Purposive sampling.

2.3.4. Sample size

Sample size for the study was 30 B.Sc nursing First year fresher students.

2.4. Tool for Data Collection

Researchers developed knowledge questionnaire on importance of Mental Health. It consists of

- Demographic variables.
- Structured knowledge questionnaire on importance of Mental Health.
- Scoring and Interpretations.

2.5. Data Collection Procedure

Data collection was done in October 2022. Data was collected by means of self-structured questionnaire .At 1st day researchers had taken the pre-test approximately for 15-24 minutes to assess the knowledge regarding importance of mental health. Followed by this structured teaching programme on importance of mental health was given. After the pre-test, students were given teaching through presentation and a post -test was administered with the same questionnaire to the same group after 5 days.

3. Results

Analysis was done by SPSS with the help of descriptive and inferential method.

Table 1 Frequency & percentage distribution of Demographic variables N=30

Demographic Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	male	19	63.3%
	Female	11	36.7%
Residence	Urban	10	33.3%
	Rural	20	66.7%
Source of information	Parents	6	20%
	Teachers	11	36.7%
	Social media	8	26.7%

	Mass media	5	16.7%
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Table 2 Pretest and Post test knowledge score. N=30

Pretest-posttest	Mean	Std .deviation
Pretest	11.60	3.42
Posttest	20.86	2.50

Table 3 Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme

	Paired differences N=30			T test	df	Sig
	95% confidence interval of difference					
	Mean	Std deviation	Std error Mean			
Knowledge score	Mean	Std deviation	Std error Mean			
Pre-test-post-test	9.26	3.02	0.5	10.3	8.13	16.76 29 .000

Table 4 An association of pre-test knowledge score with demographic variables N=30

Demographic variables		P value	Inference
Gender	Male	0.009	Significant
	Female		
Residence	Urban	0.004	Significant
	Rural		
Source of information	Parents	0.05	Significant
	Teachers		
	Social media		
	Mass media		

4. Discussion

The present study was undertaken to determine effectiveness of structured teaching programme on importance of knowledge of mental health among Bsc Nursing 1st year students of Govt. collage of nursing GMC Srinagar, Kashmir. The data was collected from 30 subjects. The findings of the study describes that 19(63.3%) were males and 11(36.7%) were females, 20(66.7%) belong to rural and 10(33.3%) belong to urban area and source of information were teacher 11(36.7%), social media 8(26.7%), parents 6(20%) and mass media 5(16.7%). It reveals that Pre-Test Mean Knowledge Score was 11.6 which was increased to 20.86 as Post test Mean Knowledge. Hence the mean difference of Pre test and Post test knowledge score of study subjects was 9.26 with standard deviation 3.02 and paired 'T' test value 16.76 and is highly significant at p value .000.

In the present study the researchers found there was a significant association of pre-test knowledge with demographic variables at 0.009, 0.004, 0.05 respectively. Also null Hypothesis stands cancelled and research hypothesis was proven by the study.

Similar study was conducted by Mamta & Sathish Rajamani on Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Program on Knowledge regarding Mental Health and its Problems in Children among Anganwadi workers in selected villages of district Sonapat, Haryana. The study findings reveal with regard to the group the pre - test value is 13.28 (SD= \pm 3.67) and the post-test value is 33.31 (SD= \pm 5.33). The mean difference value is 20.03. The t- value for 59 degree of freedom was 2.00 at the 'P' - value 0.00. It was significant¹⁸

5. Conclusion

From this study finding, it was concluded that structured teaching programme was effective in improving the knowledge of importance regarding mental health among Bsc nursing 1st year fresher students. This will be beneficial in early identification and prevention of mental health problems among students. Because Nursing students' mental health is a global public health concern. Insufficient knowledge and related stigma have a negative impact on mental health. Globally, mental health researches has attracted researchers' attention even in Kashmir valley conflicts have affected the youth, post covid changes among students from online to offline has really challenged the students due to screen addiction and so on for collage life and in nursing majority of students do come after they are disqualified NEET exams and this leads development of mental health issues as they don't except themselves as nursing students. Thus there is need to provide knowledge of importance of mental health in our lives, so that coping among students will increase and their mental health at primary level can be restored. Hence, the current study assessed effectiveness of knowledge regarding importance of mental health as it can be a platform for prevention and restoration of mental health among students.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

In the interest of student and professional growth.

Statement of ethical approval

Researchers has taken permission from Head of institute, Govt. collage of Nursing, GMC, and Srinagar.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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